

Smart Homes in Use: Practical Gaps and Tensions

What happens when smart home technologies meet real life?

Smart home technologies are introduced with best intentions, promising efficiency, security, lower bills, convenience and comfort and sustainability—but when implemented in real-world situations unintended consequences and contradictions often emerge. These contradictions are outlined below.

1- Smart tech assumes connectivity, skills, and funds not all users have.

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniform usability • Seamless experience • Automated savings • Aging support • Adaptive design | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill gaps • Confusing interfaces • High costs • User exclusion • Infrastructure issues | |

2- Designed for ease, smart tech meets fragmented systems and messy realities.

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless rollout • Service integration • Automation aids • Institutional readiness • User empowerment | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aging housing • Liability limits • Data gaps • Staff shortages • Tech blindspots | |

3- Data-driven automation boosts efficiency but often risks privacy and security.

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous data • Cloud AI • Remote control • Connected devices • Invisible tech | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive data • Centralized risk • Device vulnerability • Data sharing • User disempowerment | |

4- Smart home tech offers user control but risks intrusive monitoring and restriction.

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User control • Data transparency • Vulnerable support • Informed consent • Trust building | | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constant monitoring • Opaque data • Power control • Default surveillance • Trust erosion | |

5- Automation seeks to optimize routines but often misses the complex, social realities of home life.

Automation	VS	Everyday life
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unpredictable life • Beyond predictions • Comfort-driven • Shared homes • Tech resistance • Experience-based • Changing routines • Partial control 		

6- Smart homes promise sustainability but are undermined by hardware waste and rapid tech turnover.

Sustainability	VS	E-waste and obsolescence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast obsolescence • Hidden emissions • Frequent upgrades • Toxic waste • Non-repairable 		

7- Smart tech aims to reduce energy but boosts consumption.

Energy efficiency	VS	Increased consumption
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience increases • Moral licensing • Always-on • Hidden energy • Device growth • Overrides waste • Rollout focus • Comfort-driven 		

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This Fact Sheet is part of the SMARTUP Project: *Smart(ening up the modern) home – Redesigning power dynamics through domestic space digitalisation*. The UK consortium for this CHANSE project is co-funded between the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) and the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) [grant number: ES/X005038/1].

Consortium: Czech Academy of Sciences (CZ), Aalto University (FI), University of Göttingen (DE), University of Lodz (PL), Cardiff University (UK).
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Design and Layout: Reem Okasha, Cardiff University (UK).

Funding organisations:

CHANSE ERA-NET Co-fund programme, funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement no 101004509.

